

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF MATHEMATICS ONLINE MOBILE INTERACTIVE MATERIAL: STUDENT'S PERFORMANCE ENHANCER

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Development and Evaluation of Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material: Student's Performance Enhancer

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Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the developed Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material (MOMIM) for Grade 10 students in San Jose National High School, Antipolo City during S.Y. 2022-2023. The developed interactive material was evaluated by the fifteen (15) experts consist of Mathematics Master teachers and ICT coordinators, and fifteen (15) Mathematics teachers from San Jose National High School, Division of Antipolo City. The finding showed that the Mathematics teachers and expert respondents both agreed that the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) had Very High Acceptability with regard to pedagogical aspects, quality of content, technical aspect, and practice/ assessment/ feedback, with a grand weighted mean of 3.79 and 3.78, respectively. In addition, there was no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material). The respondents commented that the material was properly sequenced, used manipulative data, very enjoyable and fun to play, and was good for the review and recall of the students. Meanwhile, they suggested to include questions focusing on the skills to be developed by the non-numerates, provide more exercises, and improve the font size.

Keywords: *online, mobile, interactive material, Mathematics 10*

Introduction

Contemporary society necessitates pedagogical approaches that are more efficacious and afford learners increased autonomy to engage actively in their academic pursuits. The methods of imparting instruction and disseminating knowledge are being influenced by technological advancements. Until fairly recently, educational models emphasized the importance of memorization as a fundamental learning skill. Modern technology has brought about changes in the educational system and the accessibility of information.

Presently, the acquisition of knowledge necessitates proficiency in reading, communication, auditory perception, and implementation. Mobile devices now offer a comprehensive array of tools, resources, and applications tailored for educational institutions.. (Criollo, 2021).

Students of the modern period, who were raised in the digital age, have a propensity for interacting with knowledge via sensory modalities that are tailored to their own tastes. These modalities may include not just visual and auditory forms of experience, but also tactile and kinesthetic ones, as well as others. As a consequence of this, developing effective pedagogical practices for the instruction of mathematics requires the implementation of a customized framework of teaching methodologies, instructional modalities, and educational technologies, all while taking into consideration the cognitive processes by which students assimilate information from their surroundings. (Sheromova, 2020).

Because of the fast growth of information technology and the need to learn modern skills in the 21st century, the use of digital pedagogies is becoming an increasingly common practice in higher education. In order to successfully integrate technology into the field of education, Koehler and Mishra (2009) developed the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework. The framework has been tested and put into practice in a variety of schools and other learning environments. The TPACK framework provides an effective tool for analyzing the instructional environment and exemplifies the complex interaction that exists between pedagogy, technological know-how, and subject matter expertise in a manner that is adapted to the specifics of the educational context.

Weinhandl et al. (2021) posited that contemporary technologies have become an indispensable component of our society and are progressively influencing the instruction of mathematics across all educational tiers. The researchers found that teachers had several anticipated concerns and benefits regarding the use of technology in mathematics education. These included potential discrimination of students by technology, potential loss of basic mathematical knowledge and skills among students, the opportunity for teachers to acquire new technological competencies in an individual and playful manner, and the potential for technology to enhance differentiation and individualization in mathematics instruction.

Mathematics is widely regarded as the fundamental underpinning of scientific, technological, and intellectual progress. Conventional pedagogical approaches place significant emphasis on repetitive practice of mathematical problems, resulting in a dearth of comprehension and critical thinking skills among students.

In San Jose National High School, where the researcher is currently teaching, the School Testing Coordinator prepared a report of Mathematics 10 test result for S.Y. 2019-2020. Based on the result, these are the Mean Percentage Scores from first periodical test up to fourth periodical test respectively: 47.82, 53.71, 52.45, 59.55.

In light of the aforementioned literature, the researcher was motivated to undertake a study on the Development and Evaluation of Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material, with the aim of providing innovative and effective approaches to the teaching and learning process. The study sought to ascertain the potential benefits that learners could derive from the use of this interactive material in enhancing their academic performance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the developed Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material (MOMIM) for Grade 10 students in San Jose National High School, Antipolo City during S.Y. 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What were the least mastered skills of the Grade 10 Mathematics students that could be developed based on the lowest Mean Percentage Score result of the school quarterly tests during S.Y. 2019 – 2020 that were used in developing MOMIM?
2. What was the evaluation of Mathematics teachers and expert respondents on the developed Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material (MOMIM) in terms of the following criteria?
 - 2.1. pedagogical aspects;
 - 2.2. quality of content;
 - 2.3. technical aspect; and
 - 2.4. practice/ assessment/feedback?
3. Was there any significant difference between the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the developed Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material (MOMIM)?
4. What comments and suggestions were offered by the respondents to further improve the developed Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material (MOMIM)?

Literature Review

Nasharuddin, et al. (2021) stated that modern technologies are used into a variety of teaching and learning aids to increase interactivity and keep students completely engaged in the learning process. Virtual reality, augmented reality, and mixed reality are a few of the technologies used in mobile-based educational systems.

As Dinauer (2020) stated, Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework offers a structured and all-encompassing strategy for utilizing technology in the teaching process.

In addition, Setiyadi et al. (2019) claimed that the employment of mobile devices, such as Android smartphones and tablets, both as learning aids and as fundamental parts of the learning process is made possible by the interactive learning programs that have been built for these devices. Computer-based training, which is also known as computer-based learning, makes use of a variety of pertinent simulations to promote a clearer and more intuitive knowledge of the material being studied.

According to Astalini (2019), learning that is accomplished via the use of portable electronic devices, such as laptops, smartphones, and tablets, is referred to as "mobile learning." Because it provides a platform that is more malleable for mobile learning, the use of Android in the area of education marks a big step forward in terms of technical growth. Students now have the possibility to participate in studying whenever it is convenient for them and from any place thanks to the development of mobile learning platforms that are based online.

Relatively, individuals, in accordance with the constructivist view of learning, acquire meaning from their authentic experiences as well as their relationships with other people. The birth of a unique concept known as mobile learning has been made possible by the proliferation of mobile technologies. This is due to the fact that mobile technologies provide an abundance of learning experiences and unconstrained chances for engagement, independent of time or place (Yakar et al., 2020).

Furthermore, Kasim (2021) states that the employment of interactive multimedia mobile learning products as a viable medium for educational purposes is a topic that has been discussed and agreed upon.

Moreover, according to Fathoni (2020), there is a direct correlation between the rapid advancements in mobile game technology and the meteoric rise in popularity of mobile games. The expansion of the market for mobile games is not being matched by a proportional rise in the number of games that provide instructional material in equal measure. It is possible that the lack of instructional content in a game will have a detrimental influence owing to the exciting, engrossing, and habit-forming qualities that games possess. As a consequence of this, it is very necessary to provide instructional content inside a game in order to elicit a positive impact on the people that play the game.

Lastly, Widyastuti (2020) hypothesized that the game is one of the interactive multimedia artifacts that are contributing to the fast growth of the industry on a worldwide scale. The idea of using "play-based learning" may be a useful tool in assisting in the facilitation of the educational process via the use of educational games as an alternative form of interactive learning. This can be accomplished through the use of play-based learning. The objective of the educational game is to enhance students' knowledge of the course content and to provide teachers with assistance in the development of engaging alternative pedagogical strategies.

Methodology

Research Design

The method of study that was carried out by the researcher was a descriptive survey. According to McCombes (2019), the purpose of descriptive research is to produce a detailed and systematic picture of a certain population, scenario, or event. This is the aim of descriptive research. The descriptive research design is defined by a thorough analysis of current events, followed by an accurate and exact description of the observed phenomena.

The researcher chose to conduct a descriptive study in order to assess the acceptance of the newly designed Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material (MOMIM) among professionals in the field of mathematics and mathematics instructors in Mathematics 10.

Respondents

Fifteen (15) experts which are composed of Mathematics Master Teachers and ICT experts, and fifteen (15) Mathematics teachers at San Jose National High School evaluated the developed interactive material based on Pedagogical Aspects, Quality of Content, Technical Aspect, and Practice/ Feedback/ Assessment.

Instrument

The tool used in the gathering of data was the survey questionnaire that has been self-constructed by the researcher, critiqued by her research adviser, and evaluated by fifteen experts and fifteen Mathematics teachers. The survey questionnaire consisted of four criteria, namely: pedagogical aspects, quality of content, technical aspect, and practice/ assessment/ feedback.

Procedure

The researcher sent a request letter to the Schools Division Superintendent in the City Schools Division Office of Antipolo City to conduct this study. Upon the approval, she asked the principal of San Jose National High School to allow her to administer the study on the said institution and appealed for the cooperation of the involved teachers.

The researcher requested from the School Testing Coordinator a copy of a report on the Mathematics 10 test result for S.Y. 2019-2020. Since the first periodical test had the lowest mean percentage score, the researcher determined that it would be more suited to create MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) in Mathematics 10.

The researcher used a web platform that created application games. These created applications can be installed and transferred to any android mobile phones even without internet. Upon using the appropriate web platform, the researcher developed a MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) in Mathematics 10. The topics included in the study were identified as the least mastered skills/competencies from the first quarter test results during school year 2019-2020.

The researcher developed a survey questionnaire for the experts and Mathematics teacher respondents to answer. She presented the MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) to the experts and mathematics teachers before the administration of the survey questionnaire. The researcher personally administered the survey to ensure that the questionnaires were fully accomplished and retrieved right after the evaluation. After evaluation, the respondents gave comments and suggestions on how to improve the material. Statistical analysis followed afterwards. Summary of findings, conclusions and recommendations were formulated.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher herself explained and gave the informed consent to each participant before the conduct of the study. He ensured them that the information would be used with utmost confidentiality and within the purpose of the study only.

Results and Discussion

Least Mastered Skills of the Grade 10 Mathematics Students that were Developed into MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) Based on the Result of the School Quarterly Test During S.Y. 2019 – 2020.

Table 1. *Computed Mean and Rank of Least Mastered Skills Based on the Result of the School Quarterly Test During S.Y. 2019 – 2020*

<i>LC Number</i>	<i>Competencies</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Rank</i>
M10AL-le-2	Find the sum of the first nth terms in a geometric sequence.	43.90	4
M10AL-lf-2	Solve word problems in geometric sequence.	34.22	1
M10AL-lf-2	Solve real-life problems involving arithmetic sequence.	37.70	2
M10AL-lg-2	Apply the remainder and factor theorem.	45.76	5
M10AL-lj-1	Solve polynomial equations.	40.58	3

The data above illustrate that the five learning competencies for First quarter in Mathematics 10 were determined as difficult topics for the students and the skills that need to be improved and acquired by the Grade 10 students. These considers most difficult skills in Mathematics 10 were the basis of skills needed by these grade level students in the development of the MOMIM (Mathematics Online

Mobile Interactive Material).

Evaluation of Mathematics Teachers and Expert Respondents on the Developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material)

Table 2. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) as Regards Pedagogical Aspects

<i>The instructional material MOMIM ...</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Experts</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. exhibits sequence of learning steps which are pedagogically sound.	3.93	VHA	3.80	VHA
2. uses appropriate strategies and successfully engages the students.	3.87	VHA	3.87	VHA
3. can be adapted as teaching aid to develop innovative students.	3.73	VHA	3.80	VHA
4. advocates constructivist teaching-learning approach.	3.87	VHA	3.60	VHA
5. adheres to the principles associated with outcome-based education.	3.80	VHA	3.80	VHA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.84	VHA	3.77	VHA
Standard Deviation	0.39		0.44	

The Mathematics teachers and experts both evaluated the material as Very High Acceptability with weighted means of 3.84 and 3.77, and standard deviations of 0.39 and 0.44, respectively. This means that the pedagogical aspects of MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) for Mathematics 10 were very highly accepted by Mathematics teachers and experts, which implies that the strategies are appropriate, sequence of learning steps are pedagogically sound, promotes constructivist teaching-learning approach, adheres to the principles associated with outcome-based education, and can be adapted as teaching aid to develop innovative students. It also implies that a learner-centered classroom encourages students to be curious and explore topics on their own.

This supports the study of Navalta (2020), that the developed ICT-Based Instructional Material for Mathematics 9 software used a wide range of teaching strategies in e-classroom learning, could adapt different teaching styles to different learners, promoted independency of students to learn in their own ways.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) as Regards Quality of Content

<i>The instructional material MOMIM ...</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Experts</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. covers content that matches the stated objectives.	3.93	VHA	3.80	VHA
2. has an appropriate balance of skill development and conceptual understanding.	3.67	VHA	3.60	VHA
3. has an appropriate level of complexity or difficulty of content.	3.80	VHA	3.80	VHA
4. addresses various learning styles and intelligences.	3.53	VHA	3.67	VHA
5. prepares students for future real-world experiences.	3.67	VHA	3.67	VHA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.72	VHA	3.71	VHA
Standard Deviation	0.38		0.41	

The data on the table indicated that both Mathematics teachers and experts evaluated the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) for Mathematics 10 in terms of quality of content as Very High Acceptability with weighted means of 3.72 and 3.71, and standard deviations of 0.38 and 0.41, respectively. The findings showed that in terms of quality of content, the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) for Mathematics 10 has covered content that matches the stated objectives, has balance of skill development and conceptual understanding, appropriate level of complexity, addresses various learning styles and intelligences and prepares students for future real-world experiences. When instructional materials are aligned to a learner's needs and interest, it results in a more effective educational experience.

This supports the studies of Tumaliwan (2020) and Navalta (2020), contents matched the objects of the DepEd standards, presentation of content is easier to understand since it is clear and orderly sequenced based on the capability of the students that leads to mastery of topics, which later on can be applied in real-life situations.

The data on the table 4 showed that both Mathematics teachers and experts evaluated the developed Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material for Mathematics 10 in terms of technical aspect as Very High Acceptability with weighted means of 3.83 and 3.85, and standard deviations of 0.18 and 0.24, respectively. With these results, it is reflected that in terms of technical aspect, the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) for Mathematics 10 allows users to navigate through program without difficulty, users develop visual literacy, maintains high student interest and is student friendly, uses graphics that are suitable to the topics and provides enough time for students to provide answers. It implies that the material created interfaces that are simple and intuitive to use.

This support the studies of Tumaque (2018) and Tumaliwan (2020), the interactive materials were user-friendly and very easy to

transfer to other mobile phones and easy to setup. The multimedia elements like text, images, animation, and audio were maximized, aligned to the topics, and really captured the interest the students and engage them for better learning. One of the best things of these interactive materials is that students always have their phones so they can access the materials anytime and anywhere they want.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) as Regards Technical Aspect

The instructional material MOMIM ...	Respondents			
	Teachers		Experts	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. allows users to navigate through program without difficulty.	4.00	VHA	3.87	VHA
2. allows the users to develop visual literacy.	3.73	VHA	3.80	VHA
3. maintains high student interest and is student friendly.	3.80	VHA	3.80	VHA
4. uses graphics that are suitable to the topic/s.	3.60	VHA	3.87	VHA
5. provides sufficient time to answer each question	4.00	VHA	3.93	VHA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.83	VHA	3.85	VHA
Standard Deviation	0.18		0.24	

The table 5 presented that both Mathematics teachers and experts evaluated the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) for Mathematics 10 in terms of practice/ assessment/ feedback as Very High Acceptability with weighted means of 3.77 and 3.80, and standard deviations of 0.38 and 0.28, respectively. These findings showed that in terms of practice/ assessment/ feedback, the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) for Mathematics 10 promotes independent learning, has assessment that is congruent with stated objectives, provides specific answer to measure students' learning level, allows learners a chance to reassess based on initial feedback and measures learners' abilities, interests and learning styles.

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) as Regards Practice/ Assessment/ Feedback

The instructional material MOMIM ...	Respondents			
	Teachers		Experts	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. offers practices that promote independent learning.	3.87	VHA	3.87	VHA
2. has assessment that is congruent with stated objectives.	3.87	VHA	3.87	VHA
3. provides a specific answer to measure students' learning level.	3.67	VHA	3.67	VHA
4. allows learners a chance to reassess based on initial feedback.	3.73	VHA	3.93	VHA
5. applies tasks measuring learners' abilities, interests, and learning styles.	3.73	VHA	3.67	VHA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.77	VHA	3.80	VHA
Standard Deviation	0.38		0.28	

This supports the study of Navalta (2020), the answers to the questions were precise, allowing us to gauge how much the children had learned. The assessment was given enough time to be completed.

Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material)

Table 6. Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material as to Pedagogical Aspects

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	15	3.84	0.39	0.44	2.05	Fail to reject the H0	Not Significant
Experts	15	3.77	0.44				

It can be seen in the table that the critical t value with 28 degrees of freedom is 2.05 and the computed t value is 0.44. As the computed t value is less than the critical t value at the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision fails to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) in terms of pedagogical aspects.

This implies that both Mathematics teachers and experts totally agreed that in terms of pedagogical aspects, the developed MOMIM is applicable and appropriate to use by teachers to improve ways of student learning.

Based on the table 7, the computed t value of 0.09 is lower than the critical t value of 2.05. At the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision fails to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) in terms of quality of content.

This means that both Mathematics teachers and experts totally agreed that in terms of quality of content, the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) are suitable to the level of understanding of the students.

Table 7. *Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material as to Quality of Content*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	15	3.72	0.38	0.09	2.05	Fail to reject the H0	Not Significant
Experts	15	3.71	0.41				

Apparent from table 8, the computed t value of 0.34 is lower than the critical t value of 2.05, so the null hypothesis is failed to reject. It concludes at the 5% level of significance that there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) in terms of technical aspect.

Table 8. *Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material as to Technical Aspect*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	15	3.83	0.18	0.34	2.05	Fail to reject the H0	Not Significant
Experts	15	3.85	0.24				

This means that both Mathematics teachers and experts totally agreed that in terms of technical aspect, the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) made the students more interested in learning compared when using traditional pen and paper.

Table 9. *Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material as to Practice/ Assessment/ Feedback*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	15	3.77	0.38	0.22	2.05	Fail to reject the H0	Not Significant
Experts	15	3.80	0.28				

Based on the table, the computed t value of 0.22 is lower than the critical t value of 2.05. At the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision fails to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) in terms of practice/ assessment/ feedback.

This means that both Mathematics teachers and experts totally agreed that in terms of practice/ assessment/ feedback, the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material) is very acceptable for the students to be able to demonstrate improvements.

Comments and Suggestions Offered by the Respondents to Further Improve the Developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material)

Here the comments and suggestions offered by the two groups of respondents on the developed MOMIM (Mathematics Online Interactive Material).

Comments:

(a) The material is properly sequenced and questions are arranged according to the level of difficulties, learners were given ample time to answer; (b) Students will find it interesting to study and answer since it uses manipulative data with sound effect and enables them to learn more, it is easy for the students to remember the concept since there is an example given in every question; (c) The app is a great motivator for the students to develop and enhance their skills in mathematics; (d) The app is good for students' review, recall, and allow learners to reassess their answers if incorrect; (e) Enhance teachers' skills in using or dealing with ICT.

Suggestions:

(a) There may be specific questions focusing on the skills to be developed for non-numerates learners; (b) Text size of the app may still be improved, San Serif fonts may also be used to increase legibility and readability of the words/ buttons/ instructions; (c) More exercises may be provided in the corresponding topics; (d) The chances of answering a certain question may be limited so that learners will be given enough time to really solve the given problems.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The developed interactive material is very highly acceptable to the experts and Mathematics teachers in terms of pedagogical aspects, quality of content, technical aspects, and practice/ assessment/ feedback, and can really enhance the performance of the students.

The two groups of respondents demonstrated similarity in their way of determining the quality of the developed material based on their evaluation.

The developed Mathematics Online Mobile Interactive Material (MOMIM) will become very useful among the students and teachers and may even be enjoyable in classroom utilization.

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